

Corrigendum to Białas et al. “Two NLR immune receptors acquired high-affinity binding to a fungal effector through convergent evolution of their integrated domain”

Aleksandra Białas, Sophien Kamoun

The Sainsbury Laboratory, University of East Anglia, Norwich Research Park, United Kingdom

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In Białas et al. we described the *Pik* locus in grasses. We noticed that figure 2B, presenting schematic illustration of the locus in selected species, contained errors concerning the scale and coordinates of the genomic regions used in the figure. Notably 1) the intragenic region between the *Pik-1* and *Pik-2* genes in wheat is ~0.48 kbp and not “~48 Mbp” as erroneously stated in Figure 2B and results section “Genetic linkage of the *Pik* gene pair predates the split of major grass lineages”, 2) the *Pik* locus in *Oryza longistaminata* is located on contig KN541092.1, not CM003669.1; 3) the *Oryza punctata* locus is located in a different position of chromosome 11 to the one stated in the paper; 4) for *Sorghum bicolor*, we presented the locus located on chromosome 5, not 2.

The revised figure 2B and the accompanying Supplementary file 1E are presented below. For data tractability, we also included gene accession numbers in the table. Finally, we included a searchable geneious file in this revision (Supplementary file 1).

These revisions do not alter the original conclusions about orthology of the *Pik* pair across the examined species.

Figure 2B. Schematic illustration of the *Pik* locus in selected species. The schematic gene models of *Pik-1* (blue) and *Pik-2* (grey) are shown. The integrated heavy metal-associated (HMA) domain is marked with pink. Intragenic regions not included in the figure are presented with “//” together with the region’s length above. The coordinates of the regions presented in this figure are summarised in Supplementary file 1E.

Supplementary file 1E. Coordinates of genomic regions used in Figure 1B.

Abbreviation used	Species	Chromosome/ Contig/ Scaffold	Start position	End position	Visualised genes
Os	<i>Oryza sativa</i> cv. K60	Chromosome 11	27,973,977*	28,008,157*	HM035360.1 [§]
Oniv	<i>Oryza nivara</i>	Chromosome 11	23,876,142	23,892,012	ONIVA11G22690.n & ONIVA11G2270
Oglum	<i>Oryza glumaepatula</i>	Chromosome 11	26,267,105	26,285,676	OGLUM11G22320.n & OGLUM11G22330
OI	<i>Oryza longistaminata</i>	Contig KN541092.1	30,000	1	KN541092.1_FGP002 & FGP001
Opunc	<i>Oryza punctata</i>	Chromosome 11	27,924,797	27,941,875	OPUNC11G19550.n & OPUNC11G19560
Ob	<i>Oryza brachyantha</i>	Chromosome 11	15,529,280	15,547,390	OB11G27410.n & OB11G27420
Lp	<i>Leersia perrieri</i>	Chromosome 11	20,337,647	20,286,182	LPERR11G19570.n & LPERR11G19580
Ta	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Chromosome 1D	33,124,348	31,125,148	TreasCS1D02G051400 & TreasCS1D02G051500
Dg	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	Scaffold QXEO01001682.1	1,340,805	1,295,679	QXEO01001682.1_1.n & QXEO01001682.1_2
Si	<i>Setaria italica</i>	Scaffold 8	39,159,897	39,254,896	Seita.8G238800.n, Seita.8G238900, Seita.8G239300.n & Seita.8G239100
Sb	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	Chromosome 5	70,625,589	70,662,530	SORBI_3005G219700 & SORBI_3005G19900

* coordinates based on Nipponbare GCA_001433935.

[§] genebank accession number.

.n genes annotated manually.

Supplementary material

Supplementary File 1. Searchable geneious folder